

DMP for Use case 5 - Catch crops (Vanggewassen)

Version : v3 - 13 September 2024

This Data Management Plan aims to provide a brief description of the datasets associated with use case 5 - Catch crops (Vanggewassen).

DMP Authors/Contacts

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DMP Language

English

1 Brief description of the use case

The nitrate levels in our surface waters are rising again. In 2019-2020, 28% of the 760 measurement locations of the Manure Action Plan (MestActiePlan - MAP) showed at least one transgression of the threshold of 50 mg nitrate/liter. This is bad news, because excess nutrients in the surface water negatively impact drinking water production and aquatic ecology. The MAP-6 framework that regulates fertilizer use in Flanders, states that farmers should grow catch crops on their fields in winter. These are cover crops sown after the main crop to counter the leaching of nutrients, especially nitrate. Examples are winter rye, yellow mustard; and ryegrass.

Farms in Flanders have been assigned a specific target area of catch crops they have to sow each year. The MAP-6 regulates when these crops can be sown and harvested. The Flemish Land Agency is responsible for assessing whether this target area is effectively reached and whether the sowing and harvesting periods are respected. It is not efficient for them to organize field visits each year to assess this.

1.1 What needs to be monitored?

- Which (class of) catch crop is on the field between August and April

Classes (hierarchical):

- Absence winter crop:
 - Main crop residue
 - Bare soil
- Presence winter crop:
 - Winter cereals (Wheat & Barley)
 - Other winter crops (Leek, Spinach, Chervil,...)
 - Legumes
 - Leafy catch crops (White Mustard, Tagetes, Phacelia, Buckwheat, Arugula, Borage, Nyger, Oil radish, Oilseed turnip, Cow cabbage, Leaf Mustard)
 - Catch crop mixtures

- Grass-like catch crops (Grasses, Bristle Oat, Oats, Rye, Festulolium, Sudan grass, English ryegrass and white clover)
- When the catch crop id/was sown (2-week period)
- When the catch crop is/was harvested (2-week period)

Figure 1: Overview of the classification hierarchy

1.2 Where should it be monitored?

All parcels in Flanders sown with a specific main crop and included in the Single Parcel Registration.

1.3 How often should it be monitored?

Once per year

2 Modeling approach

2.1 What type of deep learning problem?

Time series classification: Takes an image as input and outputs the classification label of that image

2.2 Which model type(s) were used?

- **1D-CNN** (e.g. TempCNN; Pelletier et al., 2019) uses convolutions in the temporal dimension for feature extraction, using a fixed temporal neighborhood.
- **Time series forest** is a modified random forest model where classification is based on the calculation of temporal features across local intervals □ regular machine learning method that takes into account the temporal dimension (Deng et al., 2013)
- **Random Forest** is a non-parametric classifier known for its high accuracy and fast processing, using multiple decision trees created through a bagging approach. It assigns class labels based on the majority vote from these trees. (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016; Breiman, 2001)

References

Belgiu, M.; Drăguț, L. Random Forest in Remote Sensing: A Review of Applications and Future Directions. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* 2016, 114, 24–31, doi:10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.01.011.

Breiman, L. Random Forests. *Mach. Learn.* 2001, 45, 5–32, doi:10.1023/A:1010933404324.

Deng, H., Runger, G., Tuv, E., & Vladimir, M. (2013). A time series forest for classification and feature extraction. *Information Sciences*, 239, 142–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2013.02.030>

Jia, X., Khandelwal, A., Mulla, D. J., Pardey, P. G., & Kumar, V. (2019). Bringing automated, remote-sensed, machine learning methods to monitoring crop landscapes at scale. *Agricultural Economics*, 50(S1), 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12531>

Pelletier, C., Webb, G. I., & Petitjean, F. (2019). Temporal Convolutional Neural Network for the Classification of Satellite Image Time Series. *Remote Sensing*, 11(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11050523>

3 Data

3.1 Description of the input data

Sentinel-2 time series preprocessed via gap filling algorithms: Preprocessing involved masking clouds and shadows using the Scene Classification Layer (SCL) via a specialized kernel process (standard deviation 1.5, window size 11). To ensure a continuous signal for the models, the series were divided into monthly intervals, using the median value per period, and gaps were filled through linear interpolation. To handle edge cases at the start and end of the growing season, an extra month was added to the temporal range (July and May), with any remaining gaps filled by duplicating the nearest valid neighbor (next or previous). The resulting dataset utilized 10 spectral bands- specifically B02–04 (VIS), B05–07 (Red-edge), B08 (NIR), and B11–12 (SWIR).

Time series ranged from August to April for the winter years 2016-2017 until 2022-2023 for training and testing (see section 3.3) and for the winter year 2023-2024 for inference (see section 3.2).

3.2 Description of the output data

3.2.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: Vanggewassen-vanggewastype_Sxxx_Syyy_2023-MM-DD

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S054, S055-S117 and S118-S172.

MM-DD are the month and day of the predictions

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers characterizing catch crop (vanggewassen) types at each month (September - April) across agricultural parcels in Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Union greening measures and regional environmental regulations.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Vanggewassen > DATE >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stien.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 09/2023 - 04/2024

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Derived from Sentinel-2 monthly time series

Bands: 7 bands with prediction probability, one for each crop type: Braak, Wintergraan, Bladrijk vanggewas, Mengsel vanggewassen, Grasachtig vanggewas, Vlinderbloemige, Overig wintergewas

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset (MB): 160 MB (per monthly output)

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

3.2.2 Dataset 2

Dataset name or title: Vanggewassen-NDVI_Sxxx_Syyy_2023-MM-DD

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S054, S055-S117 and S118-S172.

MM-DD are the month and day of the predictions

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers of NDVI values at each month (September - April) across agricultural parcels in Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Union greening measures and regional environmental regulations.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Vanggewassen > DATE >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stien.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 09/2023 - 04/2024

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Extracted from Terrascope

Bands: 1 band with NDVI values

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset (MB): 26 MB (per monthly output)

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

3.2.3 Dataset 3

Dataset name or title: Vanggewassen-gewasgroep_Sxxx_Syyy_2023-MM-DD

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S054, S055-S117 and S118-S172.

MM-DD are the month and day of the predictions

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers characterizing the main crop type at each month (September - April) across agricultural parcels in Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Union greening measures and regional environmental regulations.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Vanggewassen > DATE >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

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Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 09/2023 - 04/2024

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Extracted from Terrascope

Bands: 3 bands with prediction probability, one for each main crop type: Braak, Vanggewas, Ander gewas

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset (MB): 70 MB (per monthly output)

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

3.3 Description of the reference data

General description:

At first, the main source of reference data for this use case was planned to be the 'landbouwgebruiksparcelen' dataset (cfr. Dataset 1). It contains all parcels in Flanders that are under agricultural use in a certain year. Farmers have to report which main crop and which winter crop will be put on each parcel. However, we know from random field assessments by the Agricultural

Administration (Departement Landbouw en Visserij) that about 1/3 of the fields does not contain the winter crop that was reported by the farmer, nor do we have sufficiently detailed information about the sowing and harvest date of the winter crop(s) on each field.

Therefore, the main source of reference data for this use case is the dataset from the Department of Agriculture and Fisheries, collected by the department in the context of the greening measures of the European Union and of the regional catch crop regulation (cfr. Dataset 3). From all field observations (Kopie van Data nateelten voor KU Leuven.xlsx), 5300 field observations ranging from 2016-2021 were used to train the models. We opted to use this dataset as reference data precisely because these observations are made in the field.

In addition, we have conducted a fieldwork campaign in 2021-2022. For 60 parcels, we have recorded the crop type and the stage of the crop each week from the beginning of September to the end of October (8 weeks). For another 684 parcels, we have recorded only the crop type during a single visit between November 2021 and January 2023 (cfr. Dataset 2). For 120 parcels, we have also recorded the crop type and stage from mid-February 2022 to the end of March 2022 (6 weeks). In total, 622 of these observations were used to train the models.

An additional fieldwork campaign was conducted in 2022-2023, to create a validation dataset to test the trained models on a separate year, excluded from training the training dataset (cfr. Dataset 4). In total, we recorded the crop type for 1003 parcels during a single visit between October 2022 and February 2023, of which 970 observations were used. For both field campaigns, we have used the app 'CropObserve', a citizen science app developed in the frame of the e-shape project.

In a later stage of the project, two additional datasets have been collected, which have not been fully exploited in the research: an additional dataset of the Department of Agriculture and Fisheries for the winter year 2022-2023 (cfr. Dataset 5) and a dataset collected on February 16th in 2024 (a single field work day, cfr. Dataset 6). The former consists of 4615 unfiltered reference parcels, of which the >3000 fields are labeled *mixtures*. The latter dataset contains 125 reference parcels and was collected in an active learning context, and, again, the app 'CropObserve' was used.

Figure 2: Landbouwgebruikspercelen dataset (2021), data field work campaign 2021-2022, and screenshots of the CropObserve app

3.3.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title:

Velden_DLV_controlejaren_2016-2022_v6.geojson

Dataset abstract:

This dataset was collected in the context of the greening measures of the European Union and of the regional catch crop regulation. Each parcel has an attribute with the catch crop type needed for classification. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .geojson

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:4326 - WGS84

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 2.5698151936809590

eastBoundLongitude: 5.8183645895339851

southBoundLatitude: 50.6984679279971218

northBoundLatitude: 51.4983167173238172

Temporal extent: 2016-2021

Date of last revision: 09/10/2023

Lineage: Derived from "Data nateelten voor KU Leuven - controlejaren 2016 - 2021.xlsx" (see Accompanying files). After preprocessing these observations, the labels were linked with field geometries through combining REF_ID in the excel file with ALVID in the publicly available Landbouwgebruikspelen of the corresponding year.

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- OBJECTID = unique ID
- PERCEELCAM = the year the catch crop was reported by the farmer (e.g. observation in January 2022 is linked to 2021, as the farmer has to sow in 2021)
- HFDTLT = the main/cash crop reported by the farmer, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- LBLHFDTLT = the name of the main crop
- VASTGESTEL = observed catch crop, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- GWS_VASTGESTEL = the name of the observed catch crop

Quality flags: 'HFDTLT' column is not always correct

Number of samples in the dataset: 5300

Size of the dataset (MB): 8.56

Screenshot of attribute table:

	OBJECTID	PERCEELCAM	HFDTLT	LBLHFDTLT	VASTGESTEL	GWS_VASTGE
1	2073199588	2020	91	Suikerbieten	311	Wintertarwe
2	2078543379	2020	201	Silomaïs	60	Grasland
3	2078542975	2020	202	Korrelmaïs	311	Wintertarwe
4	1756565522	2020	202	Korrelmaïs	100	Niet ingezaaid
5	2078637652	2020	202	Korrelmaïs	60	Grasland
6	2076309046	2020	901	Aardappelen (g...	311	Wintertarwe
7	2073950936	2020	901	Aardappelen (g...	311	Wintertarwe

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Data nateelten voor KU Leuven.xlsx: raw reference dataset

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > the crop codes that can be linked to the codes in 'HFDTLT' & 'VASTGESTEL'

Landbouwgebruikspercelen 2016-2021 made publicly available by Informatie Vlaanderen

Corresponding time series of Sentinel-2 (input data) for these parcels can be made available on request.

3.3.2 Dataset 2

Dataset name or title:

Velden_Emily_2021-2022_v6.geojson

Dataset abstract:

The dataset contains the parcels, visited during the 2021-2022 field campaign, that were used for model training. Each parcel has an attribute with the catch crop type needed for classification. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .geojson

Geometry: polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:4326 - WGS 84

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):*westBoundLongitude: 2.6448282820300348**eastBoundLongitude: 5.6615917894914878**southBoundLatitude: 50.7239355209153260**northBoundLatitude: 51.4971660190014546***Temporal extent:** 09/11/2021 - 11/12/2021**Date of last revision:** 09/10/2023

Lineage: Derived from *Classificatie_referentiedata_2021-2022.shp* (see Accompanying files), which was derived from linking lat/lon in the *CropObserve* surveys (see Accompanying files) to *Landbouwgebruikspercelen_2021* (Dataset 1)

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- OBJECTID = unique ID
- PERCEELCAM = the year the catch crop was reported by the farmer (e.g. observation in January 2022 is linked to 2021, as the farmer has to sow in 2021)
- HFDTLT = the main/cash crop reported by the farmer, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- LBLHFDTLT = the name of the main crop
- VASTGESTEL = observed catch crop, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- GWS_VASTGESTEL = the name of the observed catch crop
- id_eshape = id to link the field to photos from 2021-2022 (see Accompanying files). Note: not every field is linked with a photo

Quality flags: HFDTLT/LBLHFDTLT is not always correct

Number of samples in the dataset: 622

Size of the dataset (MB): 0.72

Screenshot of attribute table:

	OBJECTID	PERCEELCAM	HFDTLT	LBLHFDTLT	VASTGESTEL	GWS_VASTGE	id_eshape
1	4141	2021	60	Grasland	321	Wintergerst	1509
2	17538	2021	9516	NULL	222	Ongeidentifice...	1006
3	18837	2021	201	NULL	321	Wintergerst	1479
4	20606	2021	201	NULL	60	Grasland	990
5	20752	2021	321	Wintergerst	321	Wintergerst	1504
6	20761	2021	321	Wintergerst	321	Wintergerst	1502

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

License (if applicable): Not applicable

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up? Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > overview of the catch crop codes

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\classificatie_referentiedata.shp: raw reference data

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\CropObserve > E_shape_app_2024-08-29_retrieved.csv

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Photos > 2021-2022

Corresponding time series data to these parcels can be found in the GitHub repository or are available on request

3.3.3 Dataset 3

Dataset name or title:

Velden_Kato_2022-2023_v2.geojson

Dataset abstract:

The dataset contains the parcels, visited during the 2022-2023 field campaign, that were used for model validation. Each parcel has an attribute with the catch crop type needed for classification. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

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Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .geojson

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:4326 - WGS84

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 2.5833881904920148

eastBoundLongitude: 5.7495561177333752

southBoundLatitude: 50.7436575936725305

northBoundLatitude: 51.4952332212877764

Temporal extent: 08/10/2022 - 08/02/2023

Date of last revision: 27/08/2024

Lineage: Derived from processing of the CropObserve surveys (see Accompanying files) and linking the lat/lon in the surveys to [Landbouwgebruikspcelen](#) (2022)

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- hoofdteelt = the main/cash crop reported by the farmer, identified with a code
- teeltcode = observed catch crop, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- remarks = remarks based on the uploaded photo in the survey
- date_field = the date the observation/survey was uploaded via the CropObserve App
- ID_eshape = ID to link this observation to the accompanying photo

Quality flags: 'hoofdteelt' column is not always correct

Number of samples in the dataset: 970

Size of the dataset (MB): 1.1

Screenshot of attribute table:

	hoofdteelt	teeltcode	remarks	date_field	ID_eshape
1	9516	60	Bedekkend	2023-01-15	3406
2	201	639	Bedekkend met...	2023-01-15	3397
3	201	639	Matig bedekke...	2023-01-15	3396
4	201	639	Bedekkend met...	2023-01-15	3395
5	201	639	Bedekkend met...	2023-01-15	3394
6	201	639	Bedekkend	2023-01-15	3401

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Velden_Kato_2022-2023_v1.geojson [First version with 1003 fields instead of 970]

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\CropObserve > E_shape_app_2024-08-29_retrieved.csv

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Photos > 2022-2023

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > the crop codes that can be linked to the codes in 'teeltcode'

Corresponding time series data to these parcels can be found in the GitHub repository or are available on request

3.3.4 Dataset 4

Dataset name or title:

Velden_DLV_2022-2023.geojson

Dataset abstract:

This dataset was collected in the context of the greening measures of the European Union and of the regional catch crop regulation. Each parcel has an attribute with the catch crop type needed for classification. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stien.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .geojson

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:4326 - WGS84

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 2.6012426563614990

eastBoundLongitude: 5.7978359063763953

southBoundLatitude: 50.6897219510239907

northBoundLatitude: 51.4766544460244901

Temporal extent: 03/10/2022 - 31/01/2023

Date of last revision: 29/04/2024

Lineage: Derived from “Vanggewassen voor KU Leuven - controlejaren 2021 - 2022.xlsx” (see Accompanying files). Limited preprocessing was done on these observations and overlapping observations with the previous excel file (“Data nateelten voor KU Leuven - controlejaren 2016 - 2021.xlsx”) were removed. The labels were linked with field geometries through combining REF_ID in the excel file with ALVID in the publicly available [Landbouwgebruikspercelen](#) of the corresponding year.

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- PERCEELCAMPAGNE = the year the catch crop was reported by the farmer (e.g. observation in January 2022 is linked to 2021, as the farmer has to sow in 2021)
- REF_ID = unique ID
- AANGEGEVEN_NATEELT = catch crop reported by the farmer, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- VASTGESTELDE_NATEELT = observed catch crop, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- GWS_VASTGESTELD = the name of the observed catch crop
- CONTROLEDATUM = date at which the observation was made
- year = column derived from CONTROLEDATUM, integer with the year of this date
- month = column derived from CONTROLEDATUM, integer with month of this date
- ALVID = unique ID, linked with publicly available landgebruikspercelen

Quality flags: None

Number of samples in the dataset: 4615

Size of the dataset (MB): 7.56

Screenshot of attribute table:

	PERCEELCAMPAGNE	REF_ID	AANGEGEVEN_NATEELT	GWS_AANGEGEVEN	VASTGESTELDE_NATEELT	GWS_VASTGESTELD	CONTROLEDATUM ▲	year	month	ALVID
1	2022	1003381639	643	Gele mosterd	100	Niet ingezaaid	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	1003381639
2	2022	459993497	321	Wintergerst	321	Wintergerst	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	459993497
3	2022	1642838678	321	Wintergerst	321	Wintergerst	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	1642838678
4	2022	411215534	659	Mengsel van niet-vli...	659	Mengsel van niet-...	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	411215534
5	2022	1126227994	659	Mengsel van niet-vli...	659	Mengsel van niet-...	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	1126227994
6	2022	906085585	659	Mengsel van niet-vli...	659	Mengsel van niet-...	03/10/22 00:00:00 (R...	2022	10	906085585

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\vanggewassen controlejaren 2021_2022 voor project monitoring.xlsx: raw reference dataset

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\CropObserve > E_shape_app_2024-08-29_retrieved.csv

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > the crop codes that can be linked to the codes in 'AANGEGEVEN_NATEELT' & 'VASTGESTELDE_NATEELT'

Corresponding time series data to these parcels can be found in the GitHub repository or are available on request

3.3.5 Dataset 5

Dataset name or title:

Velden_Kato_Stien_2023-2024.geojson

Dataset abstract:

The dataset contains the parcels visited during a field day on February 16th 2024 and were used in a context of active learning. Each parcel has an attribute with the catch crop type needed for classification. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stien.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .geojson

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:4326 - WGS84

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 2.5833881904920148

eastBoundLongitude: 5.7495561177333752

southBoundLatitude: 50.7436575936725305

northBoundLatitude: 51.4952332212877764

Temporal extent: 16/02/2024

Date of last revision: 30/06/2024

Lineage: Derived from processing of the CropObserve surveys (see Accompanying files) and linking the lat/lon in the surveys to [Landbouwgebruikspcelen](#) (2023)

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- fid = unique ID
- REF_ID = unique ID that can be linked to the publicly available landbouwgebruikspcelen v2023 vector layer
- ID_eshape = ID that can be linked to the survey & its photograph in the CropObserve app
- teeltcode = observed catch crop, identified with a code (teeltcode)
- hoofdteelt = the crop name belonging to the teeltcode ('should actually be called 'nateelt')
- remarks = remarks based on the uploaded photo in the survey
- tijdsreeks controleren = observations for which the *teeltcode* label should be checked with the help of a Sentinel-2 time series
- date_field = the date the observation/survey was uploaded via the CropObserve App

Quality flags: None

Number of samples in the dataset: 125

Size of the dataset (MB): 0.13

Screenshot of attribute table:

	fid	REF_ID	ID_eshape	teeltcode	hoofdtteelt	remarks	dsreeks controlere	date_field
1	12951	1962805912	4712	0	Niet ingezaaid	Maisresten	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...
2	12960	2316567437	4709	0	Niet ingezaaid	Maisresten	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...
3	19963	590890149	4666	0	Niet ingezaaid	Maisresten	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...
4	19964	2194110997	4669	643	Gele mosterd	Bedekkend, geel	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...
5	19980	1971093651	4703	0	Niet ingezaaid	Maisresten	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...
6	20047	2316346458	4670	60	Gras	Bedekkend, gro...	NULL	16/02/24 00:00:...

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\CropObserve > E_shape_app_2024-08-29_retrieved.csv

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Photos > 2023-2024

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > the crop codes that can be linked to the codes in 'teeltcode'

Corresponding time series data to these parcels can be found in the GitHub repository or are available on request

3.3.6 Dataset 6

Dataset name or title:

VLM_landbouwgebruikspercelen_2022.shp

Dataset abstract:

These parcels are yearly inventoried in the frame of the payments of the “European agricultural subsidies” and the “Flemish legislation on manure”. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage. Not all attributes are included in the publicly available version of this dataset, but they can be obtained upon request. This dataset is similar to Dataset 1, with the difference that this dataset from 2022 and only available for the study area where the field work of 2022 was conducted (VODKA municipalities).

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops > reference data

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stien.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .shp

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:31370

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 2.5310285295841108

eastBoundLongitude: 5.9327367152024211

southBoundLatitude: 50.6742113195872221

northBoundLatitude: 51.4954579221128270

Temporal extent: 01/01/2022 - 31/12/2022

Date of last revision: 30/09/2022

Lineage: Received from VLM

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- START_DAT = start temporal validity of layer
- STOP_DAT_V = stop temporal validity of layer
- GWS_VAL1 = pre-crop (voortelt)
- GWS_VAL = main crop type (hoofdteelt)
- GWS_VAL2 = second crop (eerste nateelt)
- GWS_VAL3 = third crop (tweede nateelt)
- X_LABEL = X coordinate (EPSG 31370)
- Y_LABEL = Y coordinate (EPSG 31370)
- TH_GT = ? (not relevant)
- LANDBSTR = agricultural region in Flanders
- LANDBCODE = code for every LANDBSTR
- GEMEENTE = Municipality where the field is located
- NIS = code for every GEMEENTE
- REF_OPP = Area in hectares
- Shape_Leng = Length of parcel shape
- Shape_Area = Parcel area in m²

Quality flags: None

Number of samples in the dataset: 109 148

Size of the dataset (MB): 100

Screenshot of attribute table:

	START_DAT	STOP_DAT_V	GWS_VAL1	GWS_VAL	GWS_VAL2	GWS_VAL3	X_LABEL	Y_LABEL	TH_GT	LANDBSTR	LANDBCODE	GEMEENTE	NIS	REF_OPP	Shape_Leng	Shape_Area
1	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	NULL	201	NULL	NULL	171773,3199000...	190690,1228999...	3	Kempen	22	Putte	12029	0,72	346,4441566424...	7159,608350006
2	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	NULL	700	NULL	NULL	177513,0836000...	224126,6663999...	1	Kempen	22	Rijkevorsel	13037	5,820000000000...	1234,438316701...	58201,98660019
3	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	NULL	12	NULL	NULL	60480,2059999...	194460,6630000...	3	Vlaamse-Zands...	18	Torhout	31033	0,02	67,99121457080...	229,2463000234
4	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	60,00000000000...	8523	NULL	NULL	63778,2335000...	178880,2960000...	3	Zandleemstreek	23	Roeselare	36015	1,080000000000...	428,9810287494...	10639,77329989
5	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	NULL	60	NULL	NULL	187646,5199000...	172791,4110999...	3	Zandleemstreek	23	Lubbeek	24066	1,010000000000...	402,4210102769...	10087,79915001
6	2022-01-01 00:00...	2022-12-31 00:00...	NULL	321	659,0000000000...	NULL	28326,0492000...	173088,2097000...	3	Zandleemstreek	23	Poperinge	33021	3,610000000000...	1122,529616892...	36131,76989982

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from VLM

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\accompanying files\Teeltcodes > the crop codes that can be linked to the codes in GWS_VAL1, GWS_VAL, GWS_VAL2, GWS_VAL3

3.3.7 Dataset 7

Dataset name or title:

fielddate_opkomst.csv

Dataset abstract:

This dataset contains the fieldwork campaign conducted in 2021-2022 related to the emergence date of catch crops. For 57 parcels, the crop type and the stage of the crop each week was recorded from the beginning of September to the end of October (8 weeks). For each of these parcels, an emergence date was noted and compiled in this dataset. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage. It was only used exploratively in the thesis of Emily Buls.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops > reference_data > emergence > 2021-2022

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stein.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .csv

Geometry: /

Coordinate reference system (CRS): /

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): /

Temporal extent: 01/09/2021 - 31/10/2021

Date of last revision: July 2022

Lineage: Derived from processing of the CropObserve surveys (see Accompanying files)

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- **opkomstdatum:** emergence date for this field. Can be linked to a field id and *teeltcode* (see description accompanying files)

Quality flags: None

Number of samples in the dataset: 57

Size of the dataset (MB): 3.9×10^{-4}

Screenshot of attribute table:

	A
1	opkomstdatum
2	2021-12-17
3	2021-09-10
4	2021-11-09
5	2021-10-30
6	2021-09-01

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

under *002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\reference data\emergence\2021-2022*

id_opkomst.csv: field ids that that belong to the emergence date file (main file)

teeltcode_opkomst.csv: teeltcodes that that belong to the emergence date file (main file)

timestamps_opkomst.csv:

fapar_opkomst.csv: fapar time series for every field

fcover_opkomst.csv: fcover time series every field

ndvi_opkomst.csv: ndvi time series every field

emergence_Emily.py: script by Emily Buls

emergence_stappenplan.ipynb: script by Emily Buls

3.3.8 Dataset 8

Dataset name or title:

velden_met_waarneming_opkomst.shp

Dataset abstract:

This dataset contains the limited fieldwork campaign conducted in 2022-2023 related to the emergence date of catch crops. For 17 parcels, the crop type and the stage of the crop was recorded in three separate weeks (2022/10/22-2022/10/23, 2022/10/29, 2022/11/05). For each of these parcels, an emergence date was noted and compiled in this dataset. For some fields, there was no emergence of a catch crop. This dataset has an informative value and is not intended for enforcement or individual usage. It was not used in our own research.

Dataset locator: PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops > reference_data > emergence > 2022-2023

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

stein.heremans@inbo.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

kato.vanpoucke@inbo.be

Data format: .shp

Geometry: Polygon

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG 31370

Geographic bounding box (WGS84):

westBoundLongitude: 4.8384092

*eastBoundLongitude:*4.9080013

southBoundLatitude: 50.9996588

northBoundLatitude: 50.9996588

Temporal extent: 22/10/2022 - 05/11/2022

Date of last revision: 03/06/2023

Lineage: Derived from processing of the CropObserve surveys (see accompanying files) and linking the lat/lon in the surveys to [Landbouwgebruikspcelen](#) (2022)

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- Opkomst: emergence date for this field
- Other attributes are derived from [Landbouwgebruikspcelen](#) (2022)

Quality flags: None

Number of samples in the dataset: 17

Size of the dataset (MB): 7×10^{-3}

Screenshot of attribute table:

	START_DAT	STOP_DAT_V	GWS_VAL1	GWS_VAL	GWS_VAL2	GWS_VAL3	X_LABEL	Y_LABEL	TH_GT	LANDBSTR	LANDBCODE	GEMEENTE	NIS	REF_OPP	Shape_Leng	Shape_Area	Opkomst
1	2022-01-01 00:00:00	2022-12-31 00:00:00	NULL	901	659,000000000000...	NULL	187704,2833999...	227062,9598999...	3	Kempen	22	Merksplas	13023	2,06000000000000...	676,2229206539...	20557,55444986...	(22/10/2022)
2	2022-01-01 00:00:00	2022-12-31 00:00:00	60,00000000000000...	312	311,000000000000...	NULL	185135,6275000...	226568,8001999...	3	Kempen	22	Merksplas	13023	1,00000000000000...	477,2414491445...	9988,742550037...	06/11/2022
3	2022-01-01 00:00:00	2022-12-31 00:00:00	60,00000000000000...	312	311,000000000000...	NULL	184875,9431000...	226478,3283999...	3	Kempen	22	Merksplas	13023	5,31000000000000...	1240,411383373...	53097,32994969...	06/11/2022
4	2022-01-01 00:00:00	2022-12-31 00:00:00	60,00000000000000...	312	311,000000000000...	NULL	184650,9614000...	226399,0989000...	3	Kempen	22	Merksplas	13023	1,46000000000000...	506,2782220412...	14643,23754972...	06/11/2022
5	2022-01-01 00:00:00	2022-12-31 00:00:00	NULL	201	700,000000000000...	NULL	185424,0925999...	226083,7201000...	3	Kempen	22	Merksplas	13023	3,35000000000000...	844,8265725751...	33458,84519989...	29/10/2022

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: Available on request from Stien Heremans or Kato Vanpoucke

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any):

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

002_DMPs reference data\Use case 5 - Catch crops\reference data\emergence\2022-2023\Cropobserve_mijn_opkomst_waarnemingen.xlsx: the separate surveys collected with the CropObserve app. These surveys can be linked with their id to the photos in *PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Use cases > Reference data > Use case reference data > 002_DMPs reference data > use case 5 - catch crops > accompanying files > Photos*